

DISILICATE IMPLANT ABUTMENTS IN ESTHETIC REGION BY USING OF CAD/CAM Tİ-BASE LITHIUM

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Annotation: Three parameters are used to describe the aesthetics and health of implant restorations: residual alveolar bone, peri-implant soft tissue and material of crown. These factors must be considered for function and aesthetics. Lithium disilicate abutments offer aesthetic advantages when ceramic materials are also used for laminate veneers. This aesthetic solution uses nothing more than thin ceramic fragments but presents excellent optical properties. This clinical report describes the use of lithium disilicate restorations with laminate veneers.

Keywords: emergence profile, light-curing composite resin, aesthetic area, recontoured gingival architecture

Introduction. Single-tooth implants have become the standard in dentistry and are considered a state-of-the-art technology. Implant survival and success rates are high^{1, 2 and 3}, so aesthetic results are the main focus of interest in aesthetically sensitive areas. To achieve optimal aesthetic results, the implant should be placed in an optimal position and inclination^{4,5}. Ideally, the implant-supported restorations should mimic the appearance of the natural tooth and be symmetrical with the reference tooth. Restoration of the anterior aesthetic zone involves challenges both in the surgical and prosthetic stages of implant dentistry. Full ceramic crowns could be an ideal choice to replace natural teeth in the aesthetic area. ⁶. The use of ceramics for both abutments and crowns increases the transparency of the teeth. Implant restorations are better than those obtained with metal abutments or metal ceramic crowns ^{6, 7}. Ceramic abutments are considered

preferable to metal components because of the gray color that permeates the tissue around the implant. Recently, lithium disilicate material has been widely marketed because of the adhesive properties of this material and the preservation of tooth structure. Computer-aided design/computer-aided manufacturing (CAD/CAM) of lithium disilicate abutments has improved soft tissue response 9, 12 and 14. Lithium disilicate abutments may benefit the management of both the color and contour of soft tissue beauty using patient-specific abutments, but further investigation is needed for mechanical risks in such clinical decisions 9,10. Lithium disilicate abutments provide aesthetic advantages when ceramic materials are also used for laminate veneers. This aesthetic solution uses only thin ceramic pieces, but exhibits excellent optical properties 10,11. This clinical report describes the use of lithium disilicate restorations with laminate veneers. **Materials and methods.** The 34-year-old female patient was admitted to the clinic of the Department of Oral Implants at the University of Istanbul, complaining of a loss of the middle incisor in the upper left and a bridge in the right tooth. The patient did not report systemic disease. Laboratory tests showed good oral hygiene and low borneol (Figures 1 and 2). The first intraoral radiograph (Figure 3) and cone beam computed tomography scan (CBCT) (Figure 4) were taken. Infiltration anesthesia was applied, and the foreskin flap was subsequently raised. The 11th tooth was extracted (Figure 5). During the next surgical phase, bone-level dental implants (Camlog Screw-Line Implants from Wimsheim, Germany) were placed according to manufacturing instructions. Immediate implantation was performed at implant position 11, and delayed implantation was performed at position 21. The implant was exposed 3 months after implantation (Figure 6). All implants were clinically stable and determined not to be mobile, and a healing abutment was installed during the repair phase. Plans for prosthetics were carried out using information collected from clinical medical records, radiographs, and diagnostic gypsum. The provisioned restorations were made on a soft tissue cast to create the same contour as the cheek

surface of the adjacent tooth. At this time, there was a clear discontinuity between the contour of the provisioned restorations on the gum surface of the crown and the width of the crown. The margin of the fixture (Figure 8). The temporary abutment was connected to create a screw-fixed provisioned restoration. After creating the provisioned restoration, the soft tissue around the implant fixture in the area (11 and 21) was trimmed to create the desired gum shape (Figure 9). A photocurable composite resin has been added to fill the space for the ideal shape of the neck contour and final contour of the provisioned restoration. This procedure allowed the tissue to adapt to pressure and triggered the urge to reshape without unduly increasing its elasticity. To transfer the contours of the formed soft tissue to the photocurable composite resin filling, a temporary buttment was connected to the provisioned restoration. Prepared lithium disilicate (IPS e.max CAD, Ivoclar Vivadent, Liechtenstein, Schern) The restorations were glued directly to Ti-based abutments in laboratory conditions (Multilink Implant, Ivoclar Vivadent, Liechtenstein, Schern). Rehabilitation with implants that support a prosthesis composed of lithium disilicate. It is a prepared implant abutment in the buccal area. The implant crown was planned as a screw repair and screwed at a controlled torque of 30N as recommended by the implant provider. The screw access hole was sealed with teflon and composite restorations. The inner surfaces of laminate veneers and abutments were etched with 9% hydrofluoric acid (Ultradent Porcelain Etch, South Jordan, Utah, USA) for 90 seconds, washed with water and air-dried (Figure 12).13)) for 1 minute, followed by a layer of adhesive (Heliobond, Variolink Veneer, Ivoclar, Vivadent). Do not allow the glue to polymerize at this stage. For dental substrates, 37% phosphoric acid (Nova DFL Industry and Trade SA, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil) was used to perform a total etching technique for 30 seconds. The acid was removed with water before the surface was completely dried. The surface was air-dried to remove the solvent, and the polymerization of the adhesive layer was canceled. Resin cement (Variolink Veneer, Ivoclar,

Vivadent) was used and applied to the inner surface of the veneer. After polymerizing resin cement, the facial side and lingual side were light cured for 90 seconds, the occlusal condition was evaluated and the forward induction was confirmed. Results and considerations. To describe the beauty and health of the implant restoration, 3 parameters are used: the remaining alveolar bone, the soft tissue around the implant, and the material of the crown. These elements should be considered functional and aesthetic. In this case, the emergency profile was achieved using a provisioned implant repair according to the concept of the emergency profile, and the patient was satisfied with the end result. This method helps to improve the shape of the interdental papillae and harmonious soft tissues 8, 10, 12. Lithium disilicate is an aesthetically advantageous material for implant abutment restorations. There are few available outlook data regarding the results of lithium disilicate abutment in implant repair 13, 14, 15, 16. Therefore, this case report provides a favorable indication that CAD/CAM TiBase lithium disilicate abutment with laminate veneers for forward position will provide excellent service in the short term. The absence of reported crown breakage for lithium disilicate materials may be expected based on recently published data showing the strength and clinical behavior of these materials, in this example, their application to the front teeth. Currently, only limited clinical data related to implant-supported lithium disilicate abutments and crowns are available in the scientific literature (13, 15, 16). Restorations using lithium disilicate abutments and lithium disilicate veneers have a monolithic press structure than single restorations without compromising aesthetics. This will give you a higher light transmittance and a better restoration. The use of ceramic veneers has allowed conservative and aesthetically successful rehabilitation treatment.

Conclusion: Therefore, in order to extend the clinical life of the restorer, it is necessary to carefully follow all clinical steps.

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